

Fact Sheet: Plastics and the Triple Planetary Crisis

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Scientific evidence demonstrates that plastics and associated chemicals (hereafter referred to as plastics), including some bio-based plastics, are destabilizing the biosphere, disrupting basic Earth system processes, harming the natural environment and living organisms including humans ¹, and threatening the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment (UNHCR A/HRC/RES/48/13).

What is the Triple Planetary Crisis?

The United Nations and its Environment Programme recognize that we are facing a Triple Planetary Crisis, with irrefutable evidence for the impacts of human activities on the planet. We face the unprecedented threats of anthropogenic **climate change**, **biodiversity loss** and **pollution** driven by unsustainable production and consumption of energy, chemicals, materials, products, and technologies. Each of these crises drives profound biophysical changes to the planet and poses threats to the rights of nature, and human rights, health, and wellbeing. Combined, these three compounding contributors render the planet less hospitable and more unpredictable. Interactions between the three crises risk initiating synergistic knock-on mechanisms that hasten and exacerbate impacts.

How do plastics cause pollution?

Plastics are a source of pollution throughout their entire life cycle, with releases to air, land, and water at all stages globally ². Plastics are chemicals ³, many known to be substances of concern. This pollution begins at the extraction of feedstocks destined for the production of plastics (i.e., fossil fuels or biobased carbon sources), with releases of greenhouse gases (GHG), fracking water, oil spills, chemicals, fertilizers, and pesticides. At polymer and production stages, chemicals and micro and nanoplastics (MNPs) are released, including monomers, polymers, additives, pellets, flakes, powders, and fragments ⁴. Spills and releases also occur during transportation ⁵. During commercial, industrial and consumer use phases, plastics are intentionally and unintentionally released, e.g., via use of fishing gear, agricultural plastics; and releases and emissions of chemicals and MNPs from plastics in the environment. Further releases occur during waste management including recycling ⁶. In addition, plastics weather constantly, making these smaller particles in permanent movement, a difficult target to assess with small particles shed and chemicals liberated ⁷. Plastics pollution mitigation and remediation of habitats can also result in releases of MNPs, as well as monomers, polymers, and combined with other intentionally and unintentionally added chemicals. Plastics pollution impacts environmental and human health ⁸ via daily exposure, multiple exposure routes (e.g., contaminated food or inhalation of particles), and cumulate impacts.

How are plastics connected to climate change?

Ninety-nine % of plastics are produced from fossil feedstocks and with large volumes of fossil energy. In 2015, plastics caused 4.5% of global GHG emissions, and its global carbon footprint is expected to increase at the same speed as projected plastics production ⁹. GHG emissions (e.g., carbon dioxide and methane) occur at all stages of the plastics life cycle, from extraction and transportation of the raw materials to polymer and chemical production, plastic product conversion, energy inputs into recycling, waste incineration and uncontrolled burning, plastics removal, and remediation of contaminated ecosystems ⁹, and environmental degradation ¹⁰. Most GHG emissions occur in the early life stages of sourcing raw materials (9%) and plastic production (85%), and 6% of emissions occur during waste management ⁹. The amount of plastics in municipal solid waste streams is rapidly increasing, as are GHG emissions from waste management ¹¹. Furthermore, there is evidence that plastics may also affect climate via indirect mechanisms. Common types of microplastics, could impact albedo (or fraction of solar radiation reflected by a surface) and melting of the cryosphere via their light-absorbing properties ¹². MNPs influence biogeochemical cycles in aquatic ¹³ and terrestrial environments ¹⁴, modifying the potential C storage in soils and aquatic ecosystems ¹⁵. Not only do plastics affect climate, but climate change can affect the fate of plastics. Extreme weather events are significantly increasing plastics pollution in all ecosystems ¹⁶.

The costs of emissions of CO₂ and other GHGs from plastics production is estimated at \$341 billion (USD) annually, due to economic losses associated with climate change, environmental degradation, and human health impacts⁸.

How do plastics impact biodiversity?

Throughout its supply chain, plastics can impact biodiversity by being (un)intentionally added to products and (un)intentionally released into the environment (e.g., land, water, and air). These releases happen for example, through spillages, landfill leachate, MNPs leakages, tire wear, dumping, and sewage (sludge) applications. Macro-, micro- and nanoplastics have impacts on living organisms and community compositions, both through their physical nature and disturbances to habitats, as well as through the toxicity of plastics, particles, and associated chemicals.

Landfills and dumpsites are increasingly covering land areas, with resulting impacts on species composition and native vegetation food safety and sovereignty, and the health, rights, economic sustainability, and wellbeing of proximate human populations¹⁷. Habitat destruction occurs as plastics smother and harm important ecosystems, like coral reefs and mangroves¹⁸. Macroplastics, like fishing gear or single-use plastics debris, can result in impacts on keystone species through ingestion, entanglement, suffocation, and death, especially for endangered species¹⁹.

Plastics also affect the very foundations of food chains. In aquatic ecosystems, MNPs have deleterious effects on photosynthetic plankton²⁰. MNPs affect soil biodiversity and can drive changes in soil properties and microbial communities²¹, including changes in nutrient cycling in sediment microbes¹⁵. Microplastics can adsorb inorganic and organic contaminants²² and modify their fate (bioaccumulation, bioavailability) and toxicity. Additionally, they can promote the spread of pathogens and antibiotic resistance genes through the ecosystems, a particular concern for the agriculture sector²³.

Chemicals, including those used in plastics, have been identified as drivers of ecosystem degradation and biodiversity decline via overt toxicity mechanisms (e.g., mortality), or sublethal impacts on, for example, species interactions, and changes in food chains²⁴. Plastics additives have negative impacts on reproduction and development in humans²⁵, other mammals, birds, fish, invertebrates, and insects²⁶.

How can the Plastics Treaty complement and potentially strengthen other multilateral environmental agreements (MEAs) addressing the Triple Planetary Crisis?

There are synergies between the future Plastics Treaty and existing multilateral environmental agreements in addressing the triple planetary crisis. Several MEAs address different forms of pollution, including some aspects of the plastics problem. For instance, the **Basel, Rotterdam and Stockholm (BRS) Conventions**, the **Minamata Convention**, the **Global Framework on Chemicals**, and the **Montreal Protocol** address some chemicals used in producing plastics as well as plastics waste disposal. However, individually and collectively they lack the mandate, the level of ambition and regulatory measures required to achieve the primary objective of UNEA Resolution 5/14: to end plastics pollution. Importantly, while virtually all plastics are made of fossil fuel-based chemicals, only 1-6% of the >16 000 plastics chemicals, are regulated under existing MEAs^{3,27}. Further, almost a quarter of these chemicals are known to be hazardous³, underlining the importance of addressing these chemicals in the future plastics treaty.

Although the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)** does not directly address plastics, its subsidiary agreement (i.e., the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework) which is meant to be implemented in harmony with the CBD and its protocols calls for the reduction of pollution to levels that are not harmful, using municipal solid waste, plastics debris, litter, and microplastics as indicators (Target 7); sustainable consumption choices to reduce waste and overconsumption (Target 16); reduction of harmful incentives (for instance, subsidies given to companies to build plastic producing plants) by at least 500 billion USD per year together with scaling up positive incentives for biodiversity (Target 18). The future plastic treaty must therefore have a clear provision for mitigating biodiversity loss from plastics while recognizing the aforementioned Targets in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework to ensure synergy and prevent duplication of efforts.

In addition, as hazardous chemicals are recognized as drivers of ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss²⁴, reducing the amounts and complexity of hazardous chemicals in plastics through the Plastics Treaty will reduce the toxic footprint of plastics and these pressures on the environment.

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) aims to protect the climate system and through its Paris Agreement, there is a legally binding agreement to limit global warming by peaking and reducing GHG emissions by scientific evidence. Reducing the use of fossil fuels in all sectors of the economy is essential to achieving the target of the Convention. Ambitious globally aggregated primary plastic polymer reduction targets will reduce global GHG emissions. This, coupled with mandated safety, sustainability, essentiality and transparency criteria for polymers, products, technologies and services will support safe and sustainable design, production, consumption and disposal to enable the ambition of the Plastics Treaty to end plastics pollution.

The importance of independent and multidisciplinary science and knowledge

The **United Nations Agenda 21** (31.4.d) advocated for enhancing scientific and technological guidance at the highest levels of the UN and other global institutions, to ensure that policies and development approaches are consistent with the best available scientific knowledge. The UN High Commissioner for Human Rights emphasized the importance of ensuring the universal right to science and stressed the need for environmental policy to be rooted in impartial scientific findings, devoid of conflicts of interest. Science should support the human right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment²⁸.

There are currently two science advisory mechanisms addressing two of the identified threats, namely climate via the **Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)**, and biodiversity via **Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)**. The IPCC has emphasized that current plastics production is not in alignment with goals to cut GHG emissions associated with fossil fuels, and IPBES emphasizes growing concerns on the impacts of plastics in ecosystems. Member states have identified the need for a similar scientific panel to support knowledge sharing concerning pollution, and the **Science-Policy Panel on Chemicals and waste (SPP)** is currently being negotiated. This panel will further contribute to the management of chemicals and waste, prevent pollution, and should interface with a subsidiary science body of the future Plastics Treaty. A dedicated **science-policy interface (SPI)** is needed under the future Plastics Treaty to strengthen these other bodies, taking advantage of resources while avoiding duplication.

The Plastics Treaty can help mitigate the Triple Planetary Crisis by eliminating plastics pollution throughout the full plastics life cycle, including feedstock extraction, production, manufacture, use, transportation, and management of plastics and mitigation of unintentional releases. Reliance on robust, independent multidisciplinary science and multistakeholder knowledge is essential, and synergies between the Plastics Treaty and other MEAs can strengthen global efforts to protect planetary health, and a safe and sustainable future for humanity.

Contributors

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References

1. Villarrubia-Gómez, *et al.* Plastics Pollution and the Planetary Boundaries framework. (Preprint 2022).
2. Scientists' Coalition for an Effective Plastics Treaty. Fact Sheet: Plastic pollution at each life stage. (2023).
3. Wagner, *et al.* State of the Science on Plastic Chemicals - Identifying and Addressing Chemicals and Polymers of Concern, NTNU Open. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701706> (2024).
4. Karlsson, *et al.* The unaccountability case of plastic pellet pollution. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 129, 52–60 (2018).
5. Jayathilaka *et al.* Spatio-temporal variation of plastic pellets dispersion in the coastline of Sri Lanka: An assessment of pellets originated from the X-Press Pearl incident during the Southwest monsoon in 2021. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 184, 114145 (2022).
6. Stapleton, *et al.* Evaluating the generation of microplastics from an unlikely source: The unintentional consequence of the current plastic recycling process. *Sci. Total Environ.* 902, 166090 (2023).
7. Arp, *et al.* Weathering Plastics as a Planetary Boundary Threat: Exposure, Fate, and Hazards. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 22, 7246–7255 (2021).
8. Landrigan, *et al.* The Minderoo-Monaco Commission on Plastics and Human Health. *Ann. Glob. Health* 89, 23 (2023).
9. Cabernard, *et al.* Growing environmental footprint of plastics driven by coal combustion. *Nat. Sustain.* 5, 139–148 (2022).
10. Royer, *et al.* Production of methane and ethylene from plastic in the environment. *PLOS ONE* 13, e0200574 (2018).
11. Zhang, *et al.* Tracking the carbon flows in municipal waste management in China. *Sci. Rep.* 14, 1471 (2024).
12. Geilfus, *et al.* Distribution and impacts of microplastic incorporation within sea ice. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 145, 463–473 (2019).
13. Makin. Microplastic contamination reduces productivity in a widespread freshwater photosymbiosis. *Aquat. Biol.* 32, 13–19 (2023).
14. Rillig, *et al.* Microplastic effects on carbon cycling processes in soils. *PLOS Biol.* 19, e3001130 (2021).
15. Shen, *et al.* (Micro)plastic crisis: Un-ignorable contribution to global greenhouse gas emissions and climate change. *J. Clean. Prod.* 254, 120138 (2020).
16. Welden & Lusher. Impacts of changing ocean circulation on the distribution of marine microplastic litter. *Integr. Environ. Assess. Manag.* 13, 483–487 (2017).
17. Vavřková, *et al.* Environmental consequences and the role of illegal waste dumps and their impact on land degradation. *Land Use Policy* 89, 104234 (2019).
18. Suyadi & Manullang. Distribution of plastic debris pollution and its implications on mangrove vegetation. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 160, 111642 (2020).
19. Tekman, *et al.* Impacts of Plastic Pollution in the Oceans on Marine Species, Biodiversity and Ecosystems. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5898684.
20. Larue, *et al.* Critical Review on the Impacts of Nanoplastics and Microplastics on Aquatic and Terrestrial Photosynthetic Organisms. *Small* 17, 2005834 (2021).
21. Wei, *et al.* Meta-analysis reveals differential impacts of microplastics on soil biota. *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 230, 113150 (2022).
22. Wanner. Plastic in agricultural soils – A global risk for groundwater systems and drinking water supplies? – A review. *Chemosphere* 264, 128453 (2021).
23. Wu, *et al.* Underestimated Risks of Microplastics on the Environmental Spread of Antibiotic Resistance Genes. *ACS EST Water* 3, 1976–1979 (2023).
24. Sigmund, *et al.* Addressing chemical pollution in biodiversity research. *Glob. Change Biol.* 29, 3240–3255 (2023).
25. Trasande, *et al.* Chemicals Used in Plastic Materials: An Estimate of the Attributable Disease Burden and Costs in the United States. *J. Endocr. Soc.* 8, 163 (2024).
26. Vos, *et al.* Health Effects of Endocrine-Disrupting Chemicals on Wildlife, with Special Reference to the European Situation. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* 30, 71–133 (2000).
27. UNEP/CHW.16/INF/58, UNEP/FAO/RC/COP.11/INF/41 & UNEP/POPS/COP.11/INF/59. Global governance of plastics and associated chemicals. (2023).
28. Türk. Protect the 'right to science' for people and the planet. *Nature* 623, 9–9 (2023).